

Data and Methodology Pre-publication: A Study of the SOMA Design Process and Participatory Experience

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1 INTRODUCTION

Soma is an hour-long participatory multi-sensory experience that was developed by an interdisciplinary team of researchers, choreographers, artists and technologists including visually impaired and sighted collaborators. Soma combines dance, somatic practices and multi-person VR technologies to create a sensory experience that explores different ways of 'seeing' and 'feeling' across physical, virtual and imagined realities. In this pre-publication document, we set out the methodology for a study that examines recent developments and performances with Soma between 2020-2022.

This document is published as a supplement to a forthcoming study that will examine and discuss the experiences of Soma participants across two workshop sessions with visually impaired participants in Bristol (Sep 2021) and twelve performances at the Bloomsbury Theatre, London (9th-11th May 2022). This document has been published while the interviews were taking place and prior to the analysis of transcripts. In this publication, we describe the data capture and analysis plans. The study was ethically reviewed by University College London's Research Ethics Committee. Following approval, participants were invited to share their thoughts on Soma and their experiences.

2 MOTIVATION

As our role as researchers inherently impacts the qualitative data analysis we perform, we present our motivations.

This study seeks to explore ideas based on the following research questions:

1. How can we define inclusive practice in VR experiences?
2. Can VR be made accessible for visually impaired audiences?
3. How does including audio description in VR performance change the experience of the spectators (i.e. those not wearing a headset)?
4. Is it possible to facilitate a participatory experience / performance with VR technology which offers a cross-modal experience, which does not prioritise the visual sense?
5. What is the process or methodology that can be used to develop inclusive or accessible elements of an experience, not just as add-on features for specific groups, but intrinsic to the aesthetic or design of the piece experienced by everyone?

Working with visually impaired collaborators and participants while developing Soma has opened up questions around how to create inclusive practice with VR technology, particularly how such a currently visual centred technology can be made accessible to visually impaired creators and audiences. This process involved developing auditory representations of the virtual environment to convey virtual interactions and the integration of an audio description layer. The audio description, alongside the crafted one-to-one support and guidance participants (or *travellers*) receive from dancers, the virtual world represented in the VR headset, not only becomes available to people who

are visually impaired but also to those who are not in VR. This realisation led to the development of a *witness* role, which was trialled during the performances at Bloomsbury Theatre and which feeds into some of the early premises for Soma. These early ideas centre on “the design and facilitation of VR encounters that expand ideas and expectations of both body and technology” [1] and bring into play the immediate effect of a perceptual tension or *gap* between the visual, virtual environment and the physical, felt environment [2]. Inviting a play and dialogue between the ‘inside’ of VR and the ‘outside’, between different sensorial experiences. Soma “calls into question normative bodily-sensorial arrangements with technology and opens up expanded sensory terrain in human-techno relationships” [3].

3 PARTICIPANTS AND INTERVIEWS

The data is drawn from audio recordings of two testing workshop sessions with 6 visually impaired participants (VIPs), and a survey and interviews with a sample of participants from the 96 in total who experienced the final 12 Soma performances at Bloomsbury theatre.

3.1 Test Workshop Sessions with VIPs

The workshop participants attended one of two sessions in groups of three where they experienced a work-in-progress showing of Soma before participating in an hour long open ended discussion of their experience with the project team to inform subsequent development of the project.

3.2 Soma Participant Survey and Interviews

35 of the Soma participants completed a survey after the performance. The intention was to also interview participants immediately after the Soma experience at the Bloomsbury Theatre; however, for some participants, Soma elicited an emotional response that persisted for some time after the experience had ended. Consequently, participants were instead asked to provide an email address if they would like to participate in a followup interview. All 29 participants who provided email addresses were invited to book a 30 minute video call between the 6th and 26th June 2022, three to six weeks after their experience. All interviews were (or will be) conducted, recorded and transcribed for later analysis by the co-authors. In advance of the interview, participants were (or will be) issued with a comprehensive information pack describing the study. Participants are able to withdraw from the study at any time, while it is active and are asked to provide written consent.

Participants responded to the survey questions, which followed a likert scale, immediately after their experience of the Soma performances at the Bloomsbury Theatre.

Please mark on a scale between 1 and 5 your response to the following statements:					
What role did you take in Soma?					
I was a VR traveller			I was a VR witness		
The overall experience was					
5	4	3	2	1	
very enjoyable				not enjoyable	
5	4	3	2	1	
comfortable				awkward	
My expectations of using Virtual Reality technology were					
5	4	3	2	1	
challenged				not challenged/as expected	
I found the experience					

Please mark on a scale between 1 and 5 your response to the following statements:

5 4 3 2 1
welcoming/inclusive not welcoming

Any information I needed access the experience was

5 4 3 2 1
available at all times not available at all

I was invited to make my own choices through the Soma journey

5 4 3 2 1
strongly agree strongly disagree

I participated/engaged in the Soma journey

5 4 3 2 1
fully/as much as possible hardly/not at all

Please write any further comments here:

Participants were asked the interview questions below and were free to respond with minimal interaction from the interviewer.

VR technology and sensory perception/modality:

- a. Have you experienced VR before? Where / what?
- b. Were your expectations of VR technology met / challenged? How / why do you think that is?
- c. Did you notice when your attention was inside the VR and when it was outside the VR? Any specific moments you remember?
- d. Did you tap into your senses in a different way to usual? How / which senses were involved? Why do you think that was?

Movement, embodiment, and participatory agency:

- a. How much did you move through the whole experience? Were there some moments where you moved more / less? Why do you think that was?
- b. Did you move as much as you wanted to move, or wanted to move more / less?
- c. How much did you feel that you could make choices about how much and how you participated?

On roles - dancer/guide, witness, traveller:

- a. What was your sense of / how did you experience the different roles within the piece? I.e. the roles of witness, traveller, and dancer-guide
- b. Did you and how did you relate to or connect with the other participants who were Travellers/Witness Did you communicate with one another? How... can you give an example? How did this feel?

VR technology and sensory perception/modality:

c. Did you and how did you relate or connect with the dancer-guides? Did you communicate with the dancer-guides? How... can you give an example? Did you feel supported, invited, challenged etc by the dancer-guides? How ... can you give an example?

Inclusivity and accessibility:

- a. Did you feel included throughout the journey? Were there any moments where you didn't? Describe these moments... If you did, what do you think made you feel welcomed, comfortable, included?
- b. Did you access all the information you needed to undertake the piece? If no, what was missing?
- c. Did the voice over giving creative audio description influence your experience of VR (either from inside or outside of the headset)? How? Why do you think that was? Did you and how did you think the audio description added to the experience?

Sound and sonification:

- a. What was your experience of sound through the experience?
- b. Could you hear different layers of sound? Can you describe them? Which layers of sound worked well for you and why?
- c. Was the sound located in certain parts of the space? If yes, can you explain more about your experience of the spatial element of the sound?

Transformation, before and after:

- a. Did you feel differently after the experience to how you had felt on arriving at the theatre? Can you describe this change?

Anything else you want to say?**4 ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY**

In this study analysis will take a phenomenological approach, exploring the personal experiences of participants. Because of its fit with an inductive approach and its capacity to create a rich and nuanced view of these interviews, Braun and Clarke's framework [4] reflexive thematic analysis has been selected as the methodology for analysis. This study focuses on using a reflexive approach for analysis [5], exploring the perspectives of participants in an approach Alvesson, Hardy and Harley describe as multi-perspective practices. Notably, we anticipate a varied set of experiences and perspectives to be captured from which this study aims to draw out ideas. The analysis will examine the responses inductively, intending to explore the explicit semantic concepts introduced by participants, though consideration will also be given to latent, underlying meaning where relevant. In line with Braun and Clarke's [6] description of reflexive thematic analysis, we recognise that as researchers we play an active role in the generation of qualitative information [7]. To support this we also provide a descriptive background of the researchers taking part in this study at the end of this publication, aiming to make clear some of our perspectives and biases. The wealth of introspective resources and writing from Braun and Clarke has helped shape our approach to qualitative analysis [4].

4.1 Methodology

This methodology somewhat contrasts the peer validated approach typical of research based on grounded theory [6]. In this study, one coder will analyse all transcripts while regularly meeting with the wider team to discuss the coding process and iteratively generate themes from the transcripts using the Nvivo software. The other authors are co-creators of Soma, who were present at the showings and met the participants and/or read some/all of the interview transcripts prior to engaging in the analysis sessions. This approach aims to ensure we are generating codes and themes that draw on the knowledge and experience of the research team [8]. In line with Clarke and Braun's process for reflexive thematic analysis, the approach for analysis follows the following steps:

1. Data familiarisation period for reviewers
2. Data coding using Nvivo software
3. Generation of themes
4. Discussion between researchers on themes, reflection and development
5. Iteration around steps 2-4
6. Refining and naming themes and developing of ideas around themes
7. Writing paper; discussion of themes

5 NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Dr Lisa May Thomas is a dance and film artist working at the intersection of performance and technology whose immersive film and performance work has been experienced by audiences around the world. Lisa is a resident at the Pervasive Media Studio in Bristol, Studio Wayne McGregor QuestLab Network Artist, and a member of the Institute of Somatic Communication with Nita Little. Her practice-as-research PhD at the University of Bristol investigated the role of digital technologies in performance, combining dance-somatic and improvisation practices with multi-person VR technology. She led the VR participatory performance work Soma, alongside which she curated an online community-led resource of body-technology practices In-Body. She is developing new work on body image and avatar development, and has just launched a new immersive participatory binaural sound experience Unlocking Touch with UCL's Digital InTouch Lab. She has presented her work at numerous academic events, most recently a Panel on children, VR & embodiment for 'Bodies, Movement and AI in VR' at Goldsmiths University (2021), and for C-Dare's 'Somatic Practices and Chronic Pain' research network at Coventry University (2020).

Maisie Palmer is an undergraduate student and research intern in the Creative Technologies Lab at the University of the West of England. Combining a passion for technology and music, Maisie is interested in live sound, software and performance.

Harshadha Balasubramanian is a practice-based PhD researcher exploring the role of creativity in social and technological change, such as how artists may pave the way for inclusion and accessibility through their application of emerging technologies. Harsha's current project, funded by the London Arts and Humanities Partnership, examines the adoption of virtual reality (VR) in the creative industries, asking how creatives are forming and influencing ideas about what and who VR is for. A defining feature of Harsha's research has been foregrounding marginalised arts practices, including Audio Description, to support artists' in reflecting on and critically rethinking VR design. She is based at the Department of Anthropology, UCL, and collaborates with advisors at the Royal College of Art.

Clarice Hilton is a PhD candidate at Goldsmiths, University of London researching creative processes which centre disability and disabled creators in immersive technology, art and dance. She is working with Candoco dance company to develop a piece of work together as part of her PhD. In conjunction with further developing InteractML, a machine learning tool for designing movement interaction, for use in this context. She is a research assistant at Goldsmiths on the MOCAP Streamer project looking at how the tool could be developed to be more accessible and how machine

learning for interaction could be implemented. She is also a research assistant at Liverpool University in the CAVA. She also works as a creative technologist working in immersive interactive experiences and has shown work globally alongside creative collective Anagram at Tribeca, Sandbox Immersive Festival, Venice Film Festival and IDFA DocLab.

Prof Joseph Hyde is an Emeritus Professor of Creative Music Technology at Bath Spa University who has been working as a musician, installation artist and audio-visual performer for over 20 years. For many years he worked at the avant-garde end of electroacoustic music and more recently, has been making music using analogue technology and running Seeing Sound, one of Europe's leading audio-visual events. He regularly collaborates with dancers, theatre-makers, technologists and scientists, and until recently ran BSU's MA Sound Arts programme.

Dr Thomas Mitchell is an Associate Professor in Creative Technologies, at UWE Bristol where he leads the Creative Technologies Laboratory. He is also a resident at the Pervasive Media Studio and a Member of the Computer Science Research Centre and Bristol Robotics Laboratory. He is a co-founder of MiMU Gloves Limited, a technology start-up that he co-founded to enable musicians to perform with gestures. Connecting physicality and sound, Tom's research explores the new affordances of motion capture and extended reality technologies to inspire questions about music, art and science.

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